

WAYS FOR IMPROVING ENGLISH SPEAKING SKILLS IN A SHORT TIME.

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ABSTRACT

This article provides individuals with wide range of information to develop their English language speaking skills easily and also it gives some clear tips for speaking by the native teachers and researchers. It also explains why some students struggle with speaking fluently.

Key words: speaking skills, communication, language, speaking methods, speaking preparation.

Introduction:

Nowadays many people are learning English which is considered as an international language in the world. Since, almost all prestigious universities require international certificate especially in this language. And majority of learners struggle to improve their speaking skills or spend great deal of time to speak English fluently. This shows that they do not know the necessary methods to quickly improve their English speaking skills. And this article will teach them some methods and show them the mistakes and shortcomings they are doing.

Literature review:

Speaking is the most noticed among all language skills. Communication is enabled most effectively through speaking and this aids in the formation of first impressions. The importance of speaking, thus, cannot be undermined. Several studies on the topic of speaking skills present results concerning students' improvement of language skills. All language researchers have different views about developing speaking ability and its proficiency. To develop oral communication, information gap activities are suggested. Information gap activities have the scope of integrating all the four skills (Venkateswaren, S., 1995). If all the language production of the student is controlled from outside, he will hardly be able to transfer his knowledge from a language learning situation to a language using situation (Bygate, M. 2003). It is a fact that it is impossible to conceive of a person being communicatively competent without being linguistically competent. In order for communication to be successful, learners need to know the appropriate social conventions (Hedge, T., 2008). Working in groups is important but many students comment that they find working in groups difficult because they can never think of intelligent things to say, they can never contribute idea to the group (Singh, M.S, 2007). Apart from that some stage fright is useful to meet the challenges. But the chief cause of fear to speak in public simply is that one is not accustomed to speak in public (Carnegie, D.1962). Most importantly, how teachers work with boys and girls, how they motivate speech activities, and relate them to their personal interests and on-going life of the school day, are vital factors for the improvement of speech (The Commission on English Curriculum, 2009). Once speaking goals have been determined, next step consists of questioning how they are going to be achieved. For designing a concrete

methodology teachers need to adopt a theoretical perspective, they need to reflect on the linguistic approach that will be used in their teaching. Many authors, following the up-to-date trend of the Communicative approach, defend the interactive role of speaking and promote its teaching from a communicative perspective stressing meaning and context. In Goodwin's words: 'In "Teaching Pronunciation" the goal of instruction is threefold: to enable our learners to understand and be understood, to build their confidence in entering communicative situations, and to enable them to monitor their speech" (Goodwin, 2001: 131), also 'pronunciation is never an end in itself but a means of negotiating meaning in discourse, embedded in specific socio cultural and interpersonal contexts' (Goodwin,2001: 117).

Research Methodology:

There are variety of methods to increase proficiency in speaking. For instance, we can use direct method to improve our speaking. In this case a student should separate enough time to prepare on a daily basis. According to the research if a student practice speaking every day it will help him/her to speak in a short time. In this method the main requirements consist of following things: 1. The learner should be given short and interesting texts, tales or the answers to basic questions such as " What do you do in your free time?" or " What are your future goals?" 2. Those texts should be practiced every day by a student. 3. The pupils tell what they understand from the text or tale to someone (their teachers, friends and learner partner). If learner cannot find any partner to practice these things, they should speak loudly in front of the mirror by looking at themselves. It help them to increase their confidence while they are speaking. But it may take long time to be ready.

You should keep in mind that if you increase amount of time that you should spend on tasks which you preparing for, the result also increase according to it. You can see the diagram for this above:

Furthermore, the following task types are used most commonly in teaching speaking, but the tasks designed for each type will need to realize the purpose

And the specifications intended for its use in a learning setting.

- Read aloud tasks.
- Describing a picture story
- Spoken essay
- Oral presentation
- Interview: controlled and open
- Information gap
- Role-play

(Wier,1990)

Each task type should be assessed on its purpose, use, design and ease of implementation.

Analysis and results:

Many English students complain that they understand English, but do not feel confident enough to join a conversation. There are a number of reasons for this, which we include here along with possible solutions:

Students try to translate from their native language into English. Production "blocking" occurs due to nervousness, lack of confidence. If you remember your childhood that you were learning your mother tongue. Of course, you did a lot of mistakes and you didn't understand everything. Therefore, be confident and allow yourself to be a child again and make as many mistakes as possible and if you do not understand everything clearly it will be improved step by step. The speaker is looking for a specific word, rather than using simple language to describe what is meant. Truth — Students sometimes limit themselves by trying to find the exact translation of something they've done. However, if you are learning English, it's not necessary to always tell the truth. If you are practicing telling stories in the past, make up a story. You'll find you can speak more easily if you aren't trying to find a specific word. Besides, there are not enough conversation opportunities around the learners. In this case they should think about what they like to discuss in their own native language. They should find a friend who speaks their language and have a conversation about a topic they enjoy in their own language. Next, they have to try to reproduce the conversation in English. Learners focus on grammar and vocabulary in order to improve their speaking but spend little time for active use. If getting ready for a test is student's primary goal for learning English, put together a study group to review and prepare — in English! They should make sure their group only discusses in English. Studying and reviewing in English, even if it's just grammar, will help them become more comfortable in speaking English. Learners also should pay attention to the materials which they are using. It has a crucial role in every field. Dialogues are useful in learning standard phrases and vocabulary used in common situations.

Discussion:

In most books there are variety of methods to improve speaking. For example, according to the book which is called "How to tech speaking" by Scott Thornbury speaking can be improved by activities like writing tasks, reading aloud, making dialogs and task repetition. However, The Chinese ELS teacher Jeremy Chiron mentioned that students

should practice a lot for easy and interesting topics and they should increase the difficulty day by day in order to speak fluently in English.

An American writer Dale Carnegie said that desire and being decisive are most important factors in speaking in his book "The Quick and Easy Way to Effective Speaking. In my opinion all of the abovementioned factors are essential to speak in a short time.

Conclusion and Recommendations:

In summary, I believe that apart from those things learners who want to speak perfectly in a short time should pay attention to linguistic skills such as grammatical structures, vocabulary, and phonetics and they should be emphasized by the teachers in the classroom or language courses so that the students should know how to speak correctly.

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